

THE PATCH CLAMP METHOD CONFIGURATIONS AND PROTOCOLS FOR ASSESSING NEURONAL EXCITABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Electrophysiology serves as an indispensable instrument in the investigation of the physiological and pathological characteristics of electrically active cells and their interconnected networks. The patch clamp method exhibits remarkable flexibility and can be employed in numerous configurations to examine a spectrum of properties.

However, adequate protocols are essential for precise measurements, ensuring the accuracy and reproducibility of experiments. The diversity of cell types requires tailored approaches, adding complexity and highlighting the need for robust protocols to enrich our understanding of neural functions.

The protocols proposed by the author represent a thoughtful contribution to the study of CA1 hippocampal neurons. They are designed to align with the physiological characteristics of these neurons, allowing sufficient time for cellular recovery following each electrical stimulus, avoiding artifacts caused by cellular fatigue. The protocols take into consideration the properties of the voltage-gated channels expressed, proving to be suitable for the study of neuronal excitability.

Key words: electrophysiology, excitability, patch clamp, input resistance, action potential.

Introduction

Nearly four decades ago, the advent of the patch clamp technique marked a significant breakthrough in Cellular Physiology and Biophysics by adding experimental value to the Hodgkin–Huxley model of the squid giant axon (Hodgkin et Huxley 1952) that earned its creators the Nobel prize in physiology in 1963, serving this way as a refinement of the voltage clamp (Neher et Sakmann 1976). This novel electrophysiological approach enabled scientists to observe the behavior of individual ion channels within the cell plasma membrane in their natural environment. Initially introduced for its ability to investigate single ion channels (Neher *et al.* 1978), the patch clamp method proved to be more versatile and powerful than anticipated, leading to the development of multiple configurations (Hamill *et al.* 1981). These configurations have profoundly enhanced our understanding of cellular electrical signaling, fundamentally transforming our knowledge of both traditionally excitable cells, such as neurons (Bean 2007; Santillo 2024) and muscle cells (Kornreich 2007), as well as other cell types such as chromaffin cells (Carbone *et al.* 2019), β -cells (Fridlyand *et al.* 2009) and even going beyond to *in vivo* recordings (Wang *et al.* 2016).

The patch clamp is an electrophysiological technique used to study the electrical properties of cells, cell membranes and occasionally isolated organelles. All patch-clamp configurations rely on a very high-resistance seal between a micropipette and a membrane. The seal is usually obtained by gentle suction. Erwin Neher, Bert Sakmann and Dieter Lux developed the patch clamp in the late 1970s and early 1980s (Hamill *et al.* 1981). Neher and Sakmann received the Nobel prize in physiology in 1991 for this work (Neher 1992).

To conduct the desired studies, adequate protocols are needed. These protocols ensure precision in measurements, which is critical for achieving accuracy and reproducibility in experiments.

However, the diversity of cell types and their unique characteristics mean that there is no one-size-fits-all protocol. Each cell type may require a tailored approach, reflecting the complexity and adaptability required in electrophysiological research. This diversity in protocols adds layers of intrigue and challenge to the field, making electrophysiology a dynamic and continually evolving discipline (Kodirov 2023).

In this article, the author addresses the lack of adequate protocols to study the pyramidal neurons of the hippocampus, which remains insufficiently studied, and suggests research-based protocols that proved effective for the measurement of fundamental electrophysiological properties.

These protocols are a result of continuous experimental refinement, considering the unique properties of hippocampal neurons and ensuring precise and reliable data collection – no artifacts were recorded as a result of fatigue since adequate recovery intervals were used. The data obtained are crucial for advancing our understanding of neural function and developing new treatments for neurological disorders.

Furthermore, since these hippocampal neurons play a role in long-term memory formation, we broaden our knowledge of the underlying molecular mechanisms.

Materials and Methods

The proposed protocols are optimized for primary cultured hippocampal neurons extracted from neonatal rats at 1-2 postnatal day. The neurons selected for electrophysiological recordings exhibited prominent pyramidal morphology with well-defined dendritic processes.

In our experimental setup, whole cell currents were measured using an EPC 10 patch clamp amplifier (HEKA Elektronik Dr. Schulze GmbH, Germany). A standard patch clamp configuration was employed, consisting of an Olympus inverted microscope equipped with a Leitz micromanipulator. Experimental control was facilitated by HEKA™ PatchMaster software. Patch pipettes were pulled from borosilicate glass using a DMZ-universal puller (Zeitz-Instruments GmbH, Munich, Germany).

For the recordings, the "whole cell" configuration was employed. The resistance of the seal exceeded 1 GΩ. In voltage clamp experiments, the holding potential (HP) was set to -80 mV, while in current clamp mode, the holding current (HI) was adjusted to ensure the cell membrane potential was approximately -70 mV. The membrane potential of the cell was measured without current injection in the current clamp mode.

The Patch Clamp Method

Ion channel activity can be recorded as a deflection in the membrane potential as a result of ions leaving or entering the cell, done by intracellular recording. Control of membrane potential is necessary to record membrane currents. This configuration is called voltage clamp. An electronic feedback system is used to measure a potential and subsequently to compare it with a pre-defined potential set by the experimenter. Any deflection from the pre-set potential is instantly compensated by a current injection. This current represents the absolute value (but opposite in sign) of the ionic current through the membrane (Molleman 2003).

Voltage clamp is the most often used configuration. When instead of voltage transmembrane current is fixed by injecting a pre-defined current pulse into the cells, the configuration is called current clamp. Current clamp does not require a feedback system. When an experiment begins, after

gaining access to the cytoplasm, a switch to current clamp with no current injection allows to measure the resting membrane potential. This measurement also provides information about the vital status of the cell (Tveito *et al.* 2016). Action potentials are recorded in current clamp mode.

The patch clamp experiment could be summarized in the following steps (Hill et Stephens 2021): the pipette, after being filled with internal solution, is positioned in close proximity of a cell in the external solution and after that the pipette tip is gently pressed onto the cell membrane. Slight suction applied through the pipette enables formation of a high resistance seal (gigaseal). Such configuration is called “on-cell.” Breaking the membrane patch inside the pipette tip by brief suction makes the pipette solution diffuse into the cytoplasm. This is the so-called “whole cell” configuration. The pipette electrode comes into direct contact with the cell cytoplasm and the membrane potential can be recorded directly. The pipette resistance is relatively low, so larger currents can be injected quicker, allowing fast space clamp. A successful breaking of the patch is indicated by increased capacitive transient in the current response to the test pulse, because the surface of the whole cell is bigger than the one of the patch itself (Hille 2001).

This technique has several variations, depending on what the researcher would like to study. The inside-out and outside-out techniques are called excised patch techniques because the patch is excised (removed) from the cell body. These configurations are used to study single ion channels, while whole-cell and perforated patch allow the researcher to investigate the electrical activity of the entire cell (Hamill *et al.* 1981).

Patch-clamp configurations

a/ On-cell patch

The pipette remains tightly sealed to the cell membrane. This allows recordings of single channel currents. Ligand-gated channels that are activated by the action of drug molecules are studied by application of the drug of choice to the internal solution (Fig. 1)

b/ Inside-out patch

After the gigaseal is formed, the pipette is quickly withdrawn from the cell, ripping the patch of membrane off the cell and at the same time leaving the patch of membrane attached to the pipette. The intracellular surface of the membrane comes in contact with the external solution (Hamill *et al.* 1981). This is a useful tool to manipulate the conditions that affect the intracellular part of ion channels (Fig. 1).

c/ Whole-cell patch

The pipette remains in its place, but additional suction is applied to break that part of the cell membrane that lies inside the pipette, providing in this way access to the intracellular milieu of the cell (Neher 1992). A possible disadvantage of this configuration could be that the internal solution has larger volume in comparison to the cell, meaning that the soluble contents of the cell interior could be replaced by the internal solution after some time (dialyzing the cell contents) (Hume et Leblanc 1989). Properties of the cell which depend on soluble intracellular contents will be altered. However, there is an initial period of time, lasting approximately 10 minutes, when the cell interior can be considered intact (Fig. 1).

d/ Outside-out patch

Being in the whole cell configuration once and withdrawing the pipette slowly from the cell, would allow a round-shaped piece of membrane to bleb out from the cell. When the pipette is pulled far enough, this bleb will detach from the cell and re-arrange as a ball of membrane on the end of

the pipette, with the outside of the membrane being the surface of the ball. Outside-out patch gives the experimenter the opportunity to examine the properties of single ion channel in defined outside environment (Fig. 1).

e/ Perforated patch

This variation of the whole-cell configuration can be described as follows: a small quantity of antifungal agents (such as Amphotericin-B, Gramicidin, or β -Escin) is incorporated into the internal solution to create small perforations in the membrane within the pipette. The primary advantage of this configuration is the reduction in the dialysis of cellular contents typically observed in the whole-cell configuration. However, it also presents several disadvantages. Firstly, the access resistance is higher, which compromises current resolution, increases recording noise, and amplifies any series resistance error. Secondly, the membrane surrounding the tip of the pipette is weakened by the perforations, making it more susceptible to rupture (Spruston et Johnston 1992).

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the sequential steps involved in achieving various patch clamp configurations. Initially, a low-resistance seal is established. Application of suction results in the formation of a gigaohm seal (cell-attached mode). Disruption of the membrane via an electric pulse or suction facilitates the transition to the whole-cell configuration. Gentle retraction of the pipette leads to the formation of either an outside-out configuration or an inside-out patch (Hamill 1981).

Results

The described protocols are accurate and precise, yielding consistent results that contribute to the understanding of neuronal behavior. These protocols were used in multiple experiments conducted by Caro et al. (2011) and Caro (2023), demonstrating their reliability and effectiveness.

Voltage clamp mode:

Voltage ramp protocol was used for approximate ionic current detection. We used a ramp starting from -80 mV increasing linearly to $+80$ mV with a speed of 1.6 V/s (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Voltage ramp – a protocol used for approximate current detection. The voltage increases linearly from -80 to +80 mV over a duration of 100 ms, corresponding to a speed of 1.6 V/s.

Pulse – a square voltage clamp protocol with a sweep interval of 5 s, starting from the holding potential (HP), switching to the voltage at which the recorded current amplitude is maximal (x mV) for y ms and consequently switching to holding membrane potential (Fig. 3).

pulse for calcium current – HP = -80mV; $x = 0$ mV; $y = 50$ ms

pulse for outward potassium current – HP = -40 mV; $x = +60$ mV; $y = 500$ ms

pulse for sodium current – HP = -80 mV; $x = 0$ mV; $y = 5$ ms;

Figure 3: Pulse protocol. The square pulse lasts for $y = 5, 50$ or 500 ms for sodium, calcium, and potassium channels, respectively; starting from the holding potential (HP), switching to voltage corresponding to maximal current amplitude x mV for each current type and switching back to the holding potential.

Current-voltage (I-V) protocol is a protocol consisting of a series of voltage steps starting from the holding potential (HP) with an amplitude increasing with an increment of $\Delta V = +10$ mV with a duration of $\Delta t = 5, 50$ and 500 ms for sodium, calcium, and potassium channels, respectively. For different types of channels, we used HP = -80 mV for voltage-dependent calcium channels, HP = -90 mV for sodium currents and HP = -40 mV for outward potassium currents (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: The current-voltage (I-V) protocol comprises a sequence of voltage steps commencing from the holding potential (HP), with an increment $\Delta V = +10$ mV up to +70 mV, optimized for different voltage channels, and with a duration Δt tailored for sodium, calcium, and potassium channels.

Current clamp mode:

For the measurement of **single action potentials**, we employed a protocol with a pulse duration of 5 ms. A holding current ($I_H = \text{ca. } -25 \pm 20$ pA) was injected to clamp desired membrane potential (approximately -65 mV), and a series of current pulses with amplitude increasing in increments of $\Delta I = 25$ pA were applied with a duration of 5 ms (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Protocol for measuring single action potentials using current clamp. The protocol involves a series of current injections starting from the holding current (HI) with increments of $\Delta I = 25$ pA and a pulse duration of 5 ms. The sweep interval is maintained at 5 s.

To measure **a series of action potentials**, we employed a protocol similar to the one previously mentioned, but with a pulse duration of 300 ms (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Current clamp protocol for measurement of series of action potentials. This is a step protocol starting from holding current (HI) with increasing current injection with a step $\Delta I = 25$ pA and a duration of 300 ms. The sweep interval is maintained at 5 s.

The input resistance was measured by injecting 6 current pulses with amplitude decreasing with step of -25 pA and recording the deflection of membrane voltage as an answer to the current pulse injected. Input resistance was calculated according to Ohm's law (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Protocol for measuring input resistance. This involves a stepwise protocol with decreasing current amplitude by $\Delta I = -25$ pA. Each pulse lasts 200 ms, with a sweep interval maintained at 5 s.

Discussion

The experimental protocols described in this publication facilitated a thorough examination of single and series action potentials, as well as the measurement of input resistance in our cellular models. The utilization of a 5 ms pulse duration for single action potentials (Lacinova *et al.* 2008), coupled with an incremental ΔI of 25 pA, allowed for precise control over membrane potential changes. This approach ensured that the evoked action potentials were consistently measurable and provided reliable data for analysis.

The transition to a 300 ms pulse duration for measuring series of action potentials was designed to capture the dynamic behavior of the cells under sustained current injection. This extended pulse length revealed the firing patterns and adaptation mechanisms of the neurons, which are crucial for understanding their excitability properties. The consistency in sweep interval (5 s) across protocols ensured that the cells had adequate recovery time, minimizing potential artifacts due to cumulative effects of repetitive stimulation (Campbell *et al.* 1996).

Input resistance measurement, through the injection of six current pulses with decreasing amplitude, provided insights into the passive electrical properties of the cells, as the input resistance determines the amplitude of passive changes in membrane potential (Santillo 2024).

Overall, these findings demonstrate the robustness of the current clamp protocols described (Caro *et al.* 2011; Caro 2023). These protocols contribute to a deeper understanding of the electrophysiological properties of the neurons, offering valuable insights into their functional characteristics.

Future studies could build upon these protocols by exploring different cell types or modifying the parameters to investigate other aspects of neuronal behavior. Such advancements would further elucidate the complex interplay between electrical stimulation and cellular response, enhancing our comprehension of neural dynamics.

Conclusion

Firstly, the use of 5 ms pulse duration for single and 300 ms pulse for action potentials fired in series highlighted the adaptability and precision of our measurement protocols, allowing for comprehensive analysis of cellular excitability.

Secondly, the consistent 5 s sweep intervals ensured minimal artifacts and reliable data, which underscored the importance of recovery periods in electrophysiological studies.

Lastly, the methodical approach to measuring input resistance confirmed the validity of Ohm's law in our experimental setup, reinforcing the necessity for precise control over experimental conditions to attain reproducible results.

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